

I. EXPERIMENTAL EVALUATION

We deployed SIBCHA prototype on Amazon’s EC2 using 1000 m 4.2 x large virtual machines (VMs), each with 8 cores and up to 1 Gbps of network throughput. For the experiments to determine SIBCHA parameters, 1,000 nodes were run on 20 EC2 instances. We can thus evaluate SIBCHA performance by running 10,000 to 50,000 SIBCHA nodes on 1,000 EC2 virtualizations, each connected to 8 randomly selected peers forming a P2P network with a bandwidth of up to 20 Mbps per node. Above settings match those of OHIE [34].

A. Block size, Block Interval, and Efficient Parallel Propagation of Blocks

We first measure block propagation delay (BPD), i.e., individual block arrival delay for 99% of the node network bandwidth with 8 Mbs to 10 Mbps. We observe that for block sizes from 10 KB to 64 KB, BPD is about 1.6 ~ 2.2 seconds. It does not increase significantly with the number of nodes in the network. For example, in our experiment with 50,000 nodes, the BPD values are about 3.0 ~ 3.3 seconds for 10 ~ 20 KB blocks. These results are similar to those in OHIE. These results are similar to those in OHIE. For comparison with OHIE we use a zone size of 20 KB, a block interval of about 10 seconds per chain to generate a block and $u = 0.43$. These settings are consistent with those in OHIE.

We further check whether propagating multiple parallel blocks in SIBCHA has a significant impact on the BPD compared to propagating one single block. Fig 1(a) shows the BPD of propagating in parallel blocks of 20KB size and the results we obtained are almost the same as those in OHIE: the number of parallel propagated blocks within a certain range does not show significantly negative impact on the BPD. Take the bandwidth of 20 Mbps as example and one hardly sees significant BPD change for parallel propagation of 0 ~ 62 blocks.

Fig 1(b) depicts the effect of bandwidth occupied by parallel block propagation on BPD. The results are almost identical to those in OHIE (we use the same configuration to recover OHIE experiments). This demonstrates the significance of parallel chain design as with the same bandwidth configuration, parallel block propagation could efficiently utilize about 50% of the original bandwidth without strikingly negative impact on the BPD.

Fig. 1. BDP under node bandwidth configuration (8 ~ 20Mbps)

Fig. 2. SIBCHA THROUGHPUT (TRANSACTIONS (TXNS)/SECOND)

Fig. 3. CONFIRMATION LATENCY

Table I. SibCha vs OHIE

bandwidth(Mbps)	k	txns per second(tps)		txns throughput(Mbps)	
		OHIE	SibCha	OHIE	SibCha
8	250	960	958	3.84	3.83
12	370	1460	1454	5.84	5.82
16	500	1940	1946	7.76	7.78
20	620	2420	2435	9.68	9.74

B. Throughput

Next we check the throughput of SIBCHA. As in OHIE, we run 12000 nodes on 1000 EC2 instances, with a bandwidth configuration of 8 ~ 20Mbps per node, a block size of 20KB, a block interval of 10 seconds per chain, and an average transaction size of 500 bytes (similar to Bitcoin). For 8/12/16/20Mbps bandwidths, we set $k=250, 370, 500$ and 620 respectively ($k * blocksize / blockinterval \approx bandwidth/2$). Since k is not a power of 2, the last 48 bits of the block hash are used to determine the chain index i to which the block is assigned, $i = H(\text{block}) \bmod k$.

As shown in Fig 2, SIBCHA throughput increases linearly with bandwidth. The throughput reaches about 2435 transactions (txns) per second at a loan of 20 Mbps. Further detailed comparison with OHIE in table I says that SIBCHA and OHIE contribute almost the same throughput. Thus, characterized by its minimal interleaving of sibling chains, simple block structure, simple confirmation mechanism, and simple fork processing, SIBCHA still retains the property of high throughput, as expected.

C. Confirmation Latency

Confirmation blocks are T blocks removed from the end of the chain, e.g., $T=6$ in Bitcoin, and $T=10$ to 15 in Ether. T 's value only has an impact on confirmation latency, but not on the throughput of OHIE [34].

Our experiments measure time consumption required for a block to be confirmed in a 20 Mbps bandwidth configuration. Figure 3 shows confirmation latencies for $T=6$ to 30 which demonstrate SIBCHA's much lower acknowledgement latency than OHIE.